

Additional file 1**1. Preparation of *An. gambiae* CYP6Z3 and cloning**

Total RNA was extracted with Arcturus PicoPure Kit (Applied Biosystems, USA) from ten adult *An. gambiae* mosquitoes from the Kisumu strain [1]. Complementary DNA was prepared using Superscript III (Invitrogen) with an oligo (dT)₂₀ primer and used as a template for amplifying full-length *AgCyp6z3* with KOD DNA polymerase (Merk Chemicals). The gene-specific primers used in these high-fidelity PCRs (Table S1) were designed according to the reference *An. gambiae* PEST CYP6Z3 genome sequence (Accession number AY193727). The PCR product was ligated into pGEM T-easy vector (Promega) and sequenced on both strands. Consistent with the high frequency of polymorphism in *An. gambiae* P450s [2](Martin Nature Ref) there were 36 single nucleotide polymorphism (SNPs) compared with the reference sequence, of which three produced amino acid changes, S209G, W396L, and H411Y. For expression, the *ompA* leader sequence (*ompA*) was engineered onto the amino-terminus of the *AgCyp6z3* gene to direct the P450 into the *E. coli* outer membrane during expression as previously described [3, 4]. The *ompA*-leader was fused to *AgCyp6z3* cDNA in frame with *AgCyp6z3* initiation codon by fusion PCR using High fidelity Phusion polymerase (Scientific). The *ompA AgCyp6z3* fusion was flanked at the 5' and 3' ends with NdeI and EcoRI, respectively for ligation into NdeI/EcoRI linearised pB13 (pCWori+).

Table S1. Primers used for amplification of CYP6Z3 and *in vitro* functional characterisation

Primer	Sequence (5'-3')
CYP6Z3_forward	ATGGCTGTTTACACTCTCGCGCTCGT
CYP6Z3_reverse	TCGAATTCTCAGCATCTATGTTCTACGCGC
<i>ompA</i> +2 Forward	GGAATTCCATATGAAAAAGACAGCTATCGCG
<i>ompA</i> +2 CYP6Z3 fusion	CGCCACGAGCGCGAGAGTGTAACAGCCATCGGAGCGGCCTGCG CTACGGTAGCGAA

2. Preparation of membranes expressing P450 and AgCPR

To express functional P450, *AgCyp6z3* cloned into pB13 plasmid was co-transformed into *E. coli* JM109 cells with *An. gambiae* NADPH-cytochrome P450 reductase (*AgCPR-pACYC*). The P450 and the *AgCPR* were previously fused with *ompA* and *pelB* leader sequences respectively to direct the expressed proteins to the inner bacterial periplasm in order to form functional monooxygenase complex [3, 5, 6]. For P450 production, 200 mL *E. coli* cultures in Terrific Broth were incubated at 21°C with shaking at 120 RPM for 18–24 h after induction with 1 mM IPTG. Following expression, *E. coli* membranes containing CYP6Z3 were isolated and P450 and AgCPR content measured as previously described [3, 7]. Samples were stored in aliquots of 100 µL at –80°C. *An. gambiae* cytochrome *b5* was prepared as described previously to supplement enzyme reactions at an 8:1 M ratio, *b5*: P450 [4].

3. Inhibition screening of pyrethroids.

Inhibition screening of pyrethroid inhibitors and IC₅₀ calculations carried out according Yunta et al. 2016[8]. Variable ligand concentrations were used for IC₅₀ calculations with diethoxy fluorescein [DEF] used at ~Km (0.2 and 0.5 µM) with 0.1 µM of CYP6Z3 and CYP6Z2 respectively. DEF reactions (200 µL) were carried out in at 25 °C in 50 mM KPi at pH 7.4 containing 1 mM glucose-6-phosphate (G6P), 0.1 mM NADP+, 0.25 mM MgCl₂, and cytochrome *b5* at an 8:1 molar ratio, *b5*: P450. NADP+ and G6P were excluded from the minus NADPH controls. Three replicates of positive and negative control reactions were run for each P450/substrate combination in opaque white 96-well (flat-based) plates in triplicate. The IC₅₀ fitting calculations were performed using GraphPad Prism 6. Data were fitted to the dose-response model and plots with R²<0.95 were rejected.

Results

The co-expression of *AgCYP6Z3* (AGAP008217) and *An. gambiae* NADPH-cytochrome P450 reductase (*AgCPR*) (AGAP000500) produced 8.25 μM P450 as measured by Fe^{2+} -CO vs Fe^{2+} difference spectra [9] in membranes (Fig S1). The P450 reductase activity was in the range of 18.04 – 29.47 nmol/min/mg protein.

Fig. S1. Fe^{2+} -CO vs. Fe^{2+} difference spectrum of *E. coli* membranes expressing *AgCYP6Z3*.

Insecticide	CYP6M2	CYP6P3	CYP6P9a	CYP6P2	CYP9J5	CYP6Z3	CYP6Z2	Mean across P450s
Deltamethrin	4.2 ^a	3.2 ^a	2.6 ^a	5.0 ^a	6.1 ^a	3.4	13.9 ^a	5.5
α -cypermethrin	1.5 ^b	2.6 ^b	4.2 ^b	9.8 ^b	13.5 ^b	4.4	8.6	6.4
Etofenprox	12 ^b	8.3 ^b	8.1 ^b	4.7 ^b	8 ^b	4.8	2.8	7.0
λ -Cyhalothrin	6.6 ^b	9.6 ^b	3.7 ^b	4.8 ^b	4.2 ^b	3.3	18.6	7.2
Permethrin	8.1 ^a	6.8 ^a	5.7 ^a	8.6 ^a	6.5 ^a	3.7	13.7 ^a	7.6
Bifenthrin	5.6 ^b	3.5 ^b	8.5 ^b	10.7 ^b	2.5 ^b	17	20.7	9.8

^a Published in Yunta *et al.* 2016[8] and ^b published in Yunta *et al.* 2019[10].

Table S3. Pyrethroid metabolism by mosquito P450s

P450	% Insecticide depletion					
	Pyrethroids type I			Pyrethroids type II		
	Permethrin	Etofenprox	Bifenthrin	Deltamethrin	λ -cyhalothrin	Cypermethrin
CYP6M2 ^t	58.5 \pm 2.2	68.8 \pm 1.1	38.9 \pm 1.6	55.4 \pm 1.4	49.4 \pm 0.5	36.8 \pm 1.8
CYP6P3 ^t	100.0 \pm 0.0	99.8 \pm 0.3	76.7 \pm 0.3	98.2 \pm 0.2	83.3 \pm 15.4	98.4 \pm 0.1
CYP6P9a ^t	87.8 \pm 0.7	98.5 \pm 0.2	53.4 \pm 1.6	97.0 \pm 0.2	67.1 \pm 3.1	89.5 \pm 2.7
Mean across P450s	82.1 \pm 21.3	89.0 \pm 17.5	56.3 \pm 19.1	83.5 \pm 24.2	66.6 \pm 17.0	74.9 \pm 33.3

^t: Incubation time 2h; (mean \pm SD)

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